

ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF PHYSICAL ANTHROPOMETRIC DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITH CARDIAC BIRTH DEFECTS UP TO CARDIORESPIRATORY INTERVENTION

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Relevance: heart birth defects (HBD) are an important problem in Pediatrics due to the prevalence of pathology and the need for early surgical correction due to significant health disorders and children's disabilities [1, 4, 5, 12]. HBD - these are abnormalities of the structure of the heart and large vessels formed during embryonic development (embryopathy), as a result of which hemodynamic disturbances occur, which can lead to heart failure and dystrophic changes in body tissues [2, 6, 18, 20]. The problem of reducing the mortality of newborns with cardiac developmental disabilities and improving the prognosis of life remains relevant [3, 7, 15, 19]. Due to the development of pediatric cardiac care, the possibility of surgical treatment of newborns and infants has emerged, and successes in this area contribute to a decrease in infant mortality [8, 10, 14, 16]. Timely correction of an anatomical defect allows you to prevent the development of complications and creates conditions for the child to return to full life [9, 11, 13, 17].

Purpose. Improving the methods of taking children to surgery based on the happiness of growth and development of premature children born with a heart defect.

Materials and methods used: Children in the main research group with HBD were fed breast milk or specially adapted milk, depending on their age.

When 102 (breast milk, adapted formulas) were studied in the nutrition of children with HBD, their physical development was considered in different guruchas. The study was conducted at the ToshPTI clinic. In the period from 2020 to 2023, a comprehensive examination of 86 children aged 0 months to 3 years with a diagnosis of HBD was carried out: of this, 44 were girls (51.1%) and 42 were boys (48.8%). Cardiac birth defects (HBD) are an important problem in Pediatrics due to the prevalence of pathology and the need for early surgical correction due to significant health disorders and children's disabilities. Cardiac birth defects (HBD) are an important problem in Pediatrics due to the prevalence of pathology and the need for early surgical correction due to significant health disorders and children's disabilities. The average age of patients at the time of their first hospitalization is 1 year and 11 months (86 days to 2 years and 11 months), with an average weight of -8.5 kg (6.00 to 13.00 kg). Children under study according to age (0-12 months and 1 year-3 years) are divided into 2 study groups. Anthropometric data was analyzes on the standard curves recommended by the who.

Results: the assessment of anthropometric indicators of physical development was carried out in accordance with the WHO recommendations. In order to obtain the necessary information about the physical development of the child, several consecutive measurements of the child's physical development indicators were carried out and applied in the physical development curves obtained from the relevant data groups of the population. Thus, when the anthropometric indicators of body weight and body length/height were analyzed, at the age of 0-12 months it was found that this indicator is in 9.3% of cases-at the level of -3 standard of deviation (SD), and in 18.7% of cases – at At the same time, OQY symptoms were detected in the age group of 1 month-3 years, and, in turn, in 13.9% of cases, it was detected at the level-3 SD, and in 11.9% - 2SD boys and -3SD -28.5%, in turn -2SD -19.1% in girls. Thus, the physical development of children with HBD of both sexes with signs of HBD acquires its own characteristics. During the assessment of physical development, the following data were obtained: the indicators of body weight and body length/height of the control group according to the who were compared with the indicators of the main group and were determined as follows, the figure in question was in 0-12 months of children at the level of 6.6% - at the level of 3SD, and in boys.

Conclusion. The results obtained were statistically significant ($r < 0.05$) when compared to the control group, the rates of physical development of children of the main group were higher (1.6 times) than those of children who did not receive the proposed recommendations.

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